

PROBLEMS OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ECONOMY OF UKRAINE IN THE CONDITIONS OF WAR

Pecheniuk A.

cand. sc. (econ.), assoc. prof.,

associate professor at the department

of energy-saving technologies and energy management,

Podillia State University, Kamianets-Podilskyi

Pecheniuk V.

student of higher education,

Podillia State University, Kamianets-Podilskyi

Abstract

The essence of the sustainable development of the state in modern conditions is revealed; threats to the sustainable development of Ukraine in the conditions of the armed aggression of the Russian Federation are mentioned. The problems of decreasing investment attractiveness in the conditions of war, the problems of mass emigration of the population, the labor market, social protection of the population, health care, education and science are analyzed. The ecological consequences of the military invasion of the Russian Federation for the environment of Ukraine are analyzed. A set of measures is proposed that will improve the sustainable development of the country in modern conditions.

Keywords: sustainable development, investment attractiveness, emigration of the population, labor market, social protection of the population, ecological consequences of the war.

Sustainable development is a concept of societal development that meets the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. The main principles of sustainable development include:

- economic sustainability – the development of the economy to ensure long-term economic growth without harming the environment and social aspects;
- environmental sustainability - preservation and rational use of natural resources, reduction of negative impact on the environment, preservation of biodiversity;
- social sustainability – ensuring social justice, equality and improving the quality of life of citizens.

Sustainable development is aimed at balancing these aspects in order to achieve a harmonious and stable future.

Solving the problems associated with Russia's long-term military aggression against Ukraine should be a significant contribution to achieving the global goals of sustainable development. Since February 2022, Russian aggression against Ukraine, the occupation of new territories, missile attacks, etc. have caused significant human losses, the destruction of state, communal and private property, the disruption of logistical supply chains, which has led to huge economic losses, mass internal and external migration and decrease in the standard of living of Ukrainians. In the light of the current events in Ukraine, the world community is forced to rethink the global goals of sustainable development. In recent years, developed countries have focused attention on ecology and the environment. However, as the war in Ukraine showed, without the basic conditions – peace, sustainable economic development, justice, valuing life and human rights – other aspects may be unattainable. Therefore, the first priorities of sustainable development during the war became the socio-economic goals of the state's development [1].

As of the beginning of 2024, Russia's massive missile strikes on the civilian and critical infrastructure of Ukraine caused damages totaling more than \$135 billion. As a result of the hostilities, 20,000 high-rise buildings and 151,000 private houses were destroyed or damaged. 3,505 health infrastructure facilities were also affected, of which 970 were completely destroyed. The Ministry of Foreign Affairs noted that the responsibility for all the destruction and loss of human lives obviously lies with Russia, which will have to pay for it [2].

Today, investment attractiveness is a key indicator of the efficiency of the country's economy, as investments play an important role in the sustainable development and stability of the state. Political instability, military actions due to the Russian invasion, the crisis related to COVID-19, corruption and the growth of the shadow economy have significantly reduced the activity of foreign investors in Ukraine. Despite these difficulties, Ukraine, following the course of European integration, continues to implement reforms to improve the investment climate.

Currently, the investment climate in Ukraine is weak, and there is a tendency for it to deteriorate. However, despite all the challenges, Ukraine offers significant opportunities for foreign investors. Among the advantages are the high qualification of the workforce, the availability of natural resources, active economic reforms and the country's strategic location. To ensure stable development of investment attractiveness, Ukraine needs to reform the economy and improve the business environment. Important steps include ending the war, improving the legal system, fighting corruption, protecting intellectual property rights, and promoting entrepreneurship and innovation [3].

A modern business in Ukraine that is attractive for investment should have the following characteristics: significant export potential, stable demand in the do-

mestic market, an established financial model for expansion into foreign markets, effective strategic management, as well as a clear investment budget (amount, purpose, expected effect). After the end of the war, the three most promising sectors may look as follows: information technology, construction and the agricultural sector [4].

The mass emigration of Ukrainians due to the full-scale Russian invasion has become an economic and humanitarian challenge not only for Ukraine, but also for partner states that have received millions of forcibly displaced people. Some Ukrainians who went abroad have already returned home, others have integrated into the society of a new country for them, and some are just now leaving Ukraine.

According to our data, the number of those who are currently emigrating is increasing. According to the Ukrainian Ministry of Foreign Affairs, as of June 21, 2023, there are 8,177,000 Ukrainian citizens abroad, which is about 20% of the population of Ukraine as of February 24, 2022. Almost half of them are in three countries: Poland (22%), Germany (15%) and the USA (11%). Only 6% of Ukrainians abroad are on consular records.

It is obvious that the return of millions of Ukrainian citizens home will require significant efforts from the Ukrainian authorities and partner states, in particular, the creation of favorable conditions in the sphere of security, humanitarian aid, and the economy [5].

Economic crises significantly affect the labor market, causing an increase in unemployment and a decrease in labor income. Business surveys show that the effects of the corona crisis and full-scale war have caused staff shortages, but for different reasons and with different consequences. This is likely due to a greater contraction of the labor market compared to the economic downturn following a full-scale invasion. According to NBU estimates, in 2023, the number of the workforce among the civilian population aged 15-70 will decrease by more than a quarter compared to 2021. Almost half of this decline was caused by external migrants dropping out of the labor force. Mobilization, demographic losses, occupation, and the transition of the population to an economically inactive status also played a significant role. The reduction in labor force participation was widespread in all regions of Ukraine, most notably in regions with active hostilities [6].

Ukraine's economy has always been vulnerable to exchange rate fluctuations, which is a significant factor in inflation. In the conditions of martial law, the foreign exchange market has become one of the most vulnerable segments of the financial market, as the panicked mood of the population and business instantly causes a frenetic demand for foreign currency. Therefore, ensuring the stability of the exchange rate has become a serious challenge for the country's central bank, because it is an important component of the stability of the entire financial system.

The NBU used international experience to prevent panic in the foreign exchange market in the first days of the full-scale invasion of Russia, in particular by establishing a fixed exchange rate regime, introducing

bans or restrictions on cash and non-cash foreign exchange transactions, as well as carrying out foreign exchange interventions by selling foreign currency. These measures contributed to the stabilization of the exchange rate, which allowed the NBU to gradually relax currency restrictions without provoking devaluation sentiments. However, long-term maintenance of a fixed exchange rate regime creates certain imbalances in the foreign exchange market and depletes gold and foreign exchange reserves.

The gradual improvement of the structure of the balance of payments due to the growth of exports will ensure an increase in the supply of foreign currency on the market and create conditions for a return to the floating exchange rate regime and currency liberalization [7].

In the conditions of military operations, business needs state support and its programs. Classic market financing is now available to businesses that have been able to adapt to current conditions, reorganize their business models and demonstrate positive cash flow or will have it in the near future.

The main tool for financing relocation programs, especially for small businesses, is grants. Approximately 30% of the relocated enterprises, or about 1,300 companies, which is 0.4-0.5% of the total number of businesses, moved to the west of Ukraine, in particular to Lviv.

When relocating abroad, there are opportunities to take advantage of preferential taxation, to receive funds for the purchase of land plots or equipment. Businesses can receive compensation for costs already incurred to rebuild their business in Europe. Although this is a complex and bureaucratic process, there are already examples when entrepreneurs received 20% to 40% compensation for their reconstruction costs [8].

In the conditions of martial law, one of the main tasks of the state is to protect the population from problems caused by the political conflict. The state is obliged to provide its citizens with everything necessary for life, so the state authorities need to find effective mechanisms and effective methods of social protection. Given that the country is in a difficult financial situation, this problem becomes especially urgent.

In the medium-term perspective, social policy reforms will be aimed at strengthening social protection of various categories of the population and comprehensive regulation of the social protection system.

The main tasks for the coming years include:

- analysis and determination of approaches to increase the level of provision of the subsistence minimum for low-income families, taking into account the financial capabilities of the state budget;
- ensuring maximum targeting and availability of social support for those who need it;
- transformation of social support programs into a single basic social assistance with unified criteria for calculating the family's total income and its financial and property status;
- improvement of the mechanisms of support for vulnerable segments of the population;
- ensuring timely and full funding of pension payments and their annual indexation;

- regulation of the pension system, determination of the location and ratio of all types of payments and benefits, terms of their appointment, calculation and payment;
- reformatting of solidarity pensions and determination of uniform approaches to calculation of insurance pensions for all categories of citizens;
- completion of the unification of the administration of payments in the social insurance system through the Pension Fund of Ukraine;
- development of the system of social services as a key tool for helping people who have fallen into difficult life circumstances, in particular due to the full-scale invasion of the Russian Federation into Ukraine, and need enhanced psychosocial assistance [9].

War always leaves a deep mark in human history, affecting all spheres of life. Its most serious impact is manifested on the mental health of people who experience constant stress due to uncertainty, threat to life and fear of the future. In modern Ukraine, stress has become an integral part of the life of many people and the entire nation.

Prolonged armed conflict, aggression of another country, occupation of territories, torture and abuse seriously affect the psycho-emotional state of the population, which can lead to distress, anxiety and depressive disorders. In a state of distress, a person cannot fully adapt to stressful events, which disrupts the normalization of his emotional and physical state.

Studies show that the level of anxiety and depression among Ukrainians has increased significantly since the beginning of the war. According to the Ministry of Health of Ukraine, as of 2023, more than 10 million people will need psychological help. Anxiety and depressive disorders not only impair quality of life, but can also have long-term effects on mental and physical health.

Vulnerable population groups, such as veterans, children, the elderly and people living in conflict zones, need special attention. It is important to improve the system of psychological support and access to psychological help to ensure proper treatment and rehabilitation of victims of war distress.

It is also necessary to improve social support mechanisms aimed at ensuring the safety, stability and economic well-being of the population. This may include social protection programs, reintegration projects, and other measures aimed at reducing the impact of war on the mental health of the population [10].

One of the most vulnerable areas was education, which has not yet had time to recover from the global pandemic. Educational institutions, forced to adapt to new restrictions and threats, are faced with the task of ensuring the safety, reliability and accessibility of education in extremely difficult conditions.

According to the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, since the beginning of the full-scale invasion, 3,793 educational institutions have been affected, of which 365 were completely destroyed due to bombing and shelling.

The war called into question the availability and security of education. Many children lost the opportunity to study, and teachers, under the threat of

shelling, continued to work in regions where hostilities are ongoing or may begin. Such conditions require careful planning of educational processes and provision of proper learning conditions during the war [11].

The destruction by the armed forces of the Russian Federation of industrial facilities and urban infrastructure of Ukraine caused the release of deadly pollutants that threaten people's health. The climate crisis has clearly shown interdependence: human health depends on the health of the environment, and events in one country affect the ecological state around the world.

Ukraine is facing the triple threat of biodiversity loss, climate change and increased pollution, compounded by hostilities and destructive attacks. Ukraine recently began negotiations to join the European Union, which requires the implementation of significant environmental safeguards, and this process will determine the direction of specific reforms.

The ecological consequences of Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine are deep and far-reaching. Attacks on the environment have directly affected human lives and livelihoods. Historically, land and nature have been important assets of Ukraine. By 2022, 7% of Ukraine's territory has been set aside as protected natural areas, with plans to further increase forest massifs and nature conservation zones.

A large part of the territory of Ukraine is contaminated by land mines and unexploded ordnance. Cleanup of this area will take many decades and may be delayed due to accessibility, financial and security factors. In the coming years, this will be one of the highest priorities for Ukraine. It is important that demining is carried out in such a way as not to cause further damage to the environment. For example, mechanical demining and removal of topsoil can speed up mine removal but cause significant damage. In agricultural areas, the risk of crater formation and the release of pollutants due to detonation of mines should be carefully analyzed.

A healthy, climate- and environment-friendly Ukraine will require significant changes in many sectors of the economy, just like other countries in the world trying to solve this problem. Many structural investments and reforms will need to be decided upon and launched, even in wartime conditions.

The level of support needed to rebuild Ukraine is extraordinary. It is important that this unprecedented level of financial support meets Ukraine's environmental needs and goals. The damage caused to nature, biodiversity, air and water in Ukraine requires attention. Justice must be done, and the significant risks of nuclear, chemical and other contamination must be immediately addressed. Ukraine's support in these matters is a way to contribute to the recovery process after large-scale destruction [12].

Ensuring the sustainable development of Ukraine's economy in the conditions of war requires a comprehensive approach that covers various aspects of the economic, social and political spheres. Here is a set of measures that can contribute to sustainable development:

1) economic stabilization and business support (financial support, tax policy, diversification of the economy, public procurement);

2) support of the social sphere (social protection; employment support; ensuring adequate financing of the health care and education system);

3) infrastructure restoration (reconstruction, energy security; infrastructure projects);

4) political and administrative support (anti-corruption measures, reform of state institutions, international cooperation).

5) strategic planning and innovation (development of a long-term strategy for sustainable development, support for scientific research and introduction of the latest technologies in production, investment in education and personnel training);

6) protection of human rights and development of civil society (protection of rights and freedoms of citizens, support of non-governmental organizations and public initiatives aimed at solving social and economic problems).

These measures can ensure the stability of the development of the economy of Ukraine even in the conditions of war, contributing to the recovery and development of the country in the future.

References

1. Kapinos H., Larionova K. (2023) Problems of managing the sustainable development of Ukraine in the conditions of war. *Scientific journal «MODELING THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ECONOMIC SYSTEMS»*, 1. 93-103.

2. The total amount of damage to Ukraine's infrastructure due to Russia's aggression is more than \$135 billion. (2024) *ArmyInform*. URL: <https://armyinform.com.ua/2024/01/19/zagalna-suma-zbytkiv-infrastruktury-ukrayiny-cherez-agresiyu-rosiyi-skladaye-ponad-135-mlrd/>

3. Slavkova A.A., Kolisnyk D.R. (2023) Ukraine's investment attractiveness: realities in war conditions and prospects for post-war reconstruction. *Economy and society*, 56. URL: <https://doi.org/10.32782/2524-0072/2023-56-138>.

4. Kysliak R. (2024) Investments during the war. Who, where and why is ready to invest money in Ukraine. *RBC-Ukraine*. URL: <https://www.rbc.ua/rus/news/investitsiyi-pid-chas-viyni-hto-kudi-i-chomu-1710245929.html>.

5. The number of Ukrainians and their migration abroad due to the war. (2024) *UKRINFORM*. URL: <https://www.ukrinform.ua/rubric-ato/3732355-kilkist-ukrainciv-ta-ih-migracia-za-kordon-cerez-vijnu.html>.

6. Inflation will remain moderate and the economy will continue to recover in 2024-2026. (2024) *Inflation report of the National Bank of Ukraine*. URL: <https://bank.gov.ua/ua/news/all/inflyatsiya-zalishatimetsya-pomirnoyu-a-ekonomika-nadali-vidnovlyuvatimetsya-u-20242026-rokah--inflyatsiyniy-zvit-nbu>.

7. Derkach Yu. (2023) Use of instruments of currency regulation in the conditions of martial law. *Transformational economy*, 3(03). 21-25. URL: <https://doi.org/10.32782/2786-8141/2023-3-4>.

8. Matiushenko O. (2024) How businesses get financing during wartime. *Finclub*. URL: <https://finclub.net/ua/priama-mova/yak-biznesu-otrymaty-finansuvannia-pid-chas-viiny.html>.

9. Bezpalenko O.V. (2022) Vectors of social policy for Ukraine under the challenges of war. Problems of modern transformations. Series: economics and management, 1(4). URL: <https://doi.org/10.54929/2786-5738-2022-4-07-04>.

10. Kovalska N.A., Zhuk A.M., Korzhenko V.O. (2024) Impact of war distress in Ukraine on mental health. *International Scientific Journal «Grail of Science»*, 37. 406-410.

11. Myhal M. (2023) Education in conditions of war: challenges and prospects for Ukraine. *Website of the Institute of Analytics and Advocacy*. URL: <https://iaa.org.ua/articles/education-in-times-of-war-challenges-and-prospects-for-ukraine/>.

12. Valstrem M. (2024) Environmental agreement for Ukraine: a green future. URL: https://www.president.gov.ua/storage/j-files-storage/01/24/65/148029c127aa3b2a3fe9f482f9226118_1707492894.pdf.